

Supplementary information: Object neophilia in herring gulls in urban and rural locations

E. Inzani*, L.A. Kelley & N.J. Boogert

*Corresponding author: eli204@exeter.ac.uk

Table S1 Town locations where experimental trials were conducted, and the number of birds approached and tested.

Town	Urban classification for settlement	Number of failed trials (gull left test area immediately)	Gull did not approach	Gull pecked at object	Gull approached without pecking
Cadgwith	Rural	4	0	0	0
Cambourne	Urban	1	1	1	0
Falmouth	Urban	32	18	1	7
Hayle	Rural	2	3	0	0
Helston	Urban	3	5	0	2
Looe	Rural	9	7	3	2
Mevagissey	Rural	2	4	1	1
Mousehole	Rural	3	1	0	0
Newlyn	Rural	17	5	0	0
Newquay	Urban	13	14	2	5
Par	Rural	4	0	0	0
Penzance	Urban	4	2	1	0
Perranporth	Rural	2	0	0	0
Polzeath	Rural	5	3	0	2
Porthleven	Rural	5	7	1	1
St Ives	Urban	6	11	3	9
St Mawes	Rural	0	1	0	0
Truro	Urban	1	1	0	1
Total		113	83	13	30
Total successful observations			126		
Total observations with object interactions				43	

Table S2 Objects used in experimental trials

Object No.	Object	Object dimensions L x W x H (cm)	Common/Novel	Number of colours
1	Blue hat	23.5x20.0x6.0	Common	2
2	Green shoe	30.0x10.0x7.1	Common	3
3	Bucket and spade	15.1x10.0x19.0	Common	2
4	Kitchen brush	28.3x7.0x3.5	Common	3
5	White and blue paper	21.3x15.2x0.5	Common	4
6	Flowerpot	13.1x12.7x12.3	Common	1
7	Watering can	37.0x10.2x22.5	Common	1
8	Tennis ball	6.0x6.0x6.0	Common	2
9	Duplo pyramid covered in white patterned fabric	16.3x3.2x9.8	Novel	4
10	Bottle bottom with green card tube, bottle lid on top and metal cone inside	11.3x9.8x20.5	Novel	5
11	Duplo tall thin	12.0x3.0x19.9	Novel	9
12	Duplo dinosaur	15.0x6.4x15.5	Novel	9
13	Flowerpot with a bottle top, handle and blue lid	13.8x15.9x21.3	Novel	6
14	Cardboard-flat pieces of cardboard and lids to bottles, bottle bottom and can lid attached to make 3D structure	34.7x24.5x11.5	Novel	5
15	Duplo fort	16.5x11.0x13.8	Novel	9
16	White plastic tube with a black cardboard insert	16.2x8.5x10.6	Novel	3

Table S3 Results of binomial GLM (link=logit) testing influence of gull age and urban-rural location on the probability of which object (novel or familiar) a gull paid the most attention to throughout experimental trial. Significant predictor results are in bold. Interest scores were generated by the independent observer who double-scored all experimental trial videos (see Methods in main text).

	Estimate	Standard Error	Odds ratio	95% CI	Degrees of freedom	Z value	P-value
Intercept	-0.045	0.879	0.956	0.163-5.874			
Focal gull age juvenile (vs adult)	-0.751	1.010	0.472	0.051-3.083	2	-0.743	0.457
Focal gull age sub adult (vs adult)	-0.537	0.979	0.585	0.077-3.959	2	-0.548	0.583
Urban-Rural category	-0.478	0.889	0.620	0.095-3.401	1	-0.538	0.591
Object chosen first in trial (novel or familiar)	2.603	0.888	13.508	2.770-103.418	1	2.932	3.37e-03 ***

Table S4 Results of binomial GLM (link=logit) testing whether gull age and urban-rural location influenced the probability of which object (novel or common) a gull paid the most attention to throughout the experimental trial. Significant predictor results are in bold

	Estimate	Standard Error	Odds ratio	95% CI	Degrees of freedom	Z Value	P-value
Intercept	-0.963	1.142	0.383	0.026-3.168			
Focal gull age: juvenile (vs adult)	0.110	1.679	1.117	0.026-40.895	2	0.066	0.948
Focal gull age: sub adult (vs adult)	-1.036	1.549	0.355	0.009-6.508	2	-0.669	0.503
Urban-Rural category	-1.173	1.524	0.309	0.009-5.459	1	-0.770	0.441
Object approached first in trial (Novel or Common)	5.372	1.462	215.227	20.360-8820.727	1	3.675	<0.001 ***